

Sieves for Generating Prime \mathbf{k} -tuples and Counting Functions

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Abstract

Sieve methods for generating prime \mathbf{k} -tuples are disclosed. By direct counting based on indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the actual counts of different prime \mathbf{k} -tuples are calculated after the sieve procedures. The results, with mathematical approximations for analytic expressions but no conjectures, seem to match well with those of the prior conjectures which were mostly based on probabilities and complex methods.

The derived twin prime counting function, $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{TP}}(\mathbf{N})$, or the total twin prime pairs less than a large natural number \mathbf{N} based on the sieve method with mathematical approximations is exactly the same as that of the first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture:

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{TP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim 2\mathbf{C} \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2, \text{ where } \mathbf{C} \sim 0.660162 \text{ is the twin prime constant.}$$

Similar sieve methods are applicable to general \mathbf{k} -tuples, $(\mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_0, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_1, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_2, \dots, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_{\mathbf{k}-1})$, where \mathbf{t} is a natural number, and $\mathbf{m}_0 < \mathbf{m}_1 < \mathbf{m}_2 < \dots < \mathbf{m}_{\mathbf{k}-1}$ are even integers. The derived prime \mathbf{k} -tuple counting function, $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N})$ with $\mathbf{N} \sim \mathbf{P}^2$ for a large prime \mathbf{P} , is consistent with the prime \mathbf{k} -tuple conjecture that

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim \mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{\mathbf{k}},$$

where $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}$ when \mathbf{P} goes to infinity, $\mathbf{g} \geq 0$ is an integer, and $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P}) \geq 1$ is a rational number.

Introduction of \mathbf{g} & $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})$ leads to the indication that there can only be none, single one, or infinitely many a prime \mathbf{k} -tuple of a given form. If $\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P}) = 0$, there is none or a single prime \mathbf{k} -tuple. Otherwise, $\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P}) \geq 1$ and there is infinitely many a prime \mathbf{k} -tuple. No other finite count for prime \mathbf{k} -tuples of any particular form is possible. According to the present theory, $\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P}) \geq 1$ for all 2-tuples of the form $(\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{t}+2\mathbf{m})$, where \mathbf{t} & \mathbf{m} are natural numbers. Thus, Alphonse de Polignac's conjecture that every even number is equal to the difference of two consecutive prime numbers in an infinite number of ways is affirmed.

It's been observed that the number of sexy primes is twice as that of twin primes. This is also predicted by the $\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})$ values. Some examples of $\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})$ values are: 1 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2)$, 2 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+6)$, 4/3 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+10)$, 6/5 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+14)$, 8/3 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+30)$, 16/15 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+34)$, 4 for $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+10, \mathbf{p}+30, \mathbf{p}+40, \mathbf{p}+60)$, etc.. Several $\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})$ values of prime 2-tuples & 3-tuples have been verified by actual counts.

It's been shown that $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P})$ has positive upper & lower bounds that converge to the same limit $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}$. Methods for calculating $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P})$ values with accelerated convergences have been disclosed. Some calculated $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}$ values are: $\mathbf{C}_1=1$; $\mathbf{C}_2 \sim 1.32$; $\mathbf{C}_3 \sim 2.86$; $\mathbf{C}_4 \sim 4.15$; $\mathbf{C}_5 \sim 10.13$.

For $P=53$, $N=P^2 \sim 2900$ and $gF_{cr}(P)=1$, the calculated counts of $(p, p+2)$ and $(p, p+2, p+6)$ based on the past conjecture or this theory with mathematical approximations are $\Pi_{TP}(2900) \sim 66$ & $\Pi_{3P}(2900) \sim 21$ which are less than the actual counts of 79 & 27, respectively. However, the calculated counts based on the most accurate expression without mathematical approximations are $\Pi_{TP}(2900) \sim 76$ & $\Pi_{3P}(2900) \sim 27$ which are much closer to the actual counts.

The most accurate expression for $\Pi_{kP}(N)$ without mathematical approximations for a large natural number $N \sim P^2$ is

$$\Pi_{kP}(N) \sim [gF_{cr}(P)N / (p_1 p_2 \dots p_j)] \times (1 - k/p_{j+1})(1 - k/p_{j+2})(1 - k/p_{j+3}) \dots (1 - k/P) + \Pi_{kP}(P),$$

where $p_1 < p_2 < p_3 < \dots < P < \dots$ are all the prime numbers in order, i.e. $p_1=2, p_2=3, p_3=5, p_4=7 \dots$ etc., and p_j is the greatest prime that is less than or equal to k .

Accordingly, a more accurate equation for $\Pi_{kP}(N)$ has also been derived, and the result is

$$\Pi_{kP}(N) \sim gF_{cr}(P)C_k(P) \times \int_2^N \frac{1}{[\ln(s)]^k} ds$$

I. Introduction

It has been conjectured that there are infinitely many twin primes without proof in the past. The breakthrough work of Yitang Zhang in 2013[1,2], as well as work by James Maynard, Terence Tao and others, has made substantial progress towards proving the conjecture.[3,4]

In this paper, sieve methods are implemented for generating prime k -tuples, include 1-tuple primes, 2-tuple twin primes, etc.. With the indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the prime k -tuple counting function, $\Pi_{kP}(N)$, or the total prime k -tuples with all elements less than a large natural number N , based on the sieve method is derived.

II. Sieve for Generating Twin Primes

Except the number, 2, all the prime numbers are odd and of the form $2n+1$, where n is a natural number. The possible 2-tuple twin prime pairs must be of the form $(2n+1, 2n+3)$.

The sieve is to preclude all n values which satisfy $2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ or $2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, i.e. either $2n+1$ or $2n+3$ is a multiple of all prime numbers $p > 2$. For example,

$$2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \Rightarrow n \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

$$2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow n \equiv 2 \pmod{5},$$

$$2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} \Rightarrow n \equiv 3 \pmod{7},$$

$$2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \Rightarrow n \equiv 0 \pmod{3},$$

$$2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow n \equiv 1 \pmod{5},$$

$$2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} \Rightarrow n \equiv 2 \pmod{7},$$

$2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{11} \Rightarrow n \equiv 5 \pmod{11}$, $2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{11} \Rightarrow n \equiv 4 \pmod{11}$,
 $2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{13} \Rightarrow n \equiv 6 \pmod{13}$, $2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{13} \Rightarrow n \equiv 5 \pmod{13}$,
 $2n+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{17} \Rightarrow n \equiv 8 \pmod{17}$, $2n+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{17} \Rightarrow n \equiv 7 \pmod{17}$,
 etc.. For each prime number $p > 2$, the sieve precludes n numbers that belong to 2 of the residue classes modulo p from all the n numbers.

After precluding with the sieve up to a large prime number P , the numbers left can be calculated. For example, let $S = \{n | n \text{ is a natural number, and } 1 \leq n \leq N_n\}$. If $N_n = p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$, where $p_2 < p_3 < p_4 < \dots < p_w$ are prime numbers greater than 2, every number n in S has a unique residue vector with respect to moduli $(p_2, p_3, p_4, \dots, p_w)$ according to indication of the Chinese remainder theorem. There are total of $N_n = p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$ residue vectors. After removing n numbers that belong to 2 residue classes of each prime number up to p_w , there are exactly $N_r = (p_2-2)(p_3-2)(p_4-2)\dots(p_w-2)$ residue vectors left, representing the number of elements left from S . Thus, the ratio of the number of elements left to the original number of total elements in S is

$$N_r/N_n = (p_2-2)(p_4-2)(p_3-2)\dots(p_w-2)/(p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w) = (1-2/p_2)(1-2/p_3)(1-2/p_4)\dots(1-2/p_w)$$

If N_n is a multiple of $p_2 p_3 p_4 \dots p_w$, the above equation is the exact ratio of N_r/N_n . Otherwise, the cumulated distribution, $D_{TP}(P)$, of the numbers left from a consecutive natural number set, after sieving with prime numbers from 3 to P , is just an approximation that

$$D_{TP}(P) \sim (1-2/3)(1-2/5)(1-2/7)(1-2/11)(1-2/13)(1-2/17)\dots(1-2/P) \quad (1)$$

For any one of the left numbers n , $2n+1$ & $2n+3$ cannot be divided by all prime numbers $p \leq P$. If $2n+3 < P^2$, $(2n+1, 2n+3)$ is a twin prime 2-tuple.

It has to be cautious that those n values representing the prime pairs with one of the element smaller than or equal to P are also precluded. For example, the possible twin prime pairs after sieving with $p = 3$ must be of the form $(6n-1, 6n+1)$, and $(3, 5)$ is removed. For $p = 5$, the possible twin prime pairs after sieving with $p = 5$ must be of the form $(30n+11, 30n+13)$, $(30n+17, 30n+19)$ or $(30n+29, 30n+31)$, and $(5, 7)$ is removed. Thus, N_r is not the total numbers of twin prime pairs even if all the left numbers satisfy $2n+3 < P^2$.

To generate all twin prime pairs in between 1 and a large natural number N more efficiently without precluding the small pairs, the sieving procedure can be modified as follows:

Let $S = \{n | n \text{ is a natural number, and } 1 \leq n \leq N_n, \text{ where } N_n \sim N/2\}$, and $p_2 < p_3 < p_4 < \dots < P < \dots$ be all the prime numbers in order, i.e. $p_2=3, p_3=5, p_4=7 \dots$ etc., where $P^2 \sim N$. After first sifting all numbers except $n=1$ in S with $p_2=3$, all the remanding n numbers that satisfy $2n+3 < p_3^2 = 9$ can be retained. For every other prime number, $3 < p_i \leq P$, sifting can be performed starting from the smallest remaining number that is greater than $p_{i-1}^2/2$.

III. Twin Prime Distribution

Since

$$1-2/\mathbf{P} = (1-1/\mathbf{P})^2[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2], \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P}) = (1-1/2)^{-2}(1-1/2)^2(1-1/3)^2 (1-1/5)^2 (1-1/7)^2 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^2 \times (1-1/2^2)][(1-1/4^2)(1-1/6^2) \dots [1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]$$

$$\sim 4\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P}) \times [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-2}, \text{ where}$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P}) = (1-1/2^2)(1-1/4^2)(1-1/6^2) \dots [1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2] \quad (3)$$

is the twin prime constant according to the first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture.

For a set of all natural number from 1 to a very large number \mathbf{N} , there are $\mathbf{N}_n \sim \mathbf{N}/2$ of \mathbf{n} values in the form of $(2\mathbf{n}+1, 2\mathbf{n}+3)$. Let \mathbf{P} be the prime number such that $\mathbf{P}^2 \sim \mathbf{N}$. Then, the twin prime counting function or the total numbers of twin prime pairs between 1 and \mathbf{N} is

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P}).$$

For $\mathbf{P} > 100$, $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P})$ is about 4% of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P}^2)$. Neglecting $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P})$ for large \mathbf{N} ,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{\text{TP}}(\mathbf{P}) \sim 2\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2. \quad (4)$$

When \mathbf{P} is infinitely large, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{C} \sim 0.660162$, and Eqs. (3) & (4) are exactly the same as those of the first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture.

It's obvious that $[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2] < 1$, for all primes numbers $\mathbf{P} > 2$, and, thus, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P})$ decreases as \mathbf{P} increases. Therefore, any $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P})$ value with a finite \mathbf{P} is an upper bound of the prime constant \mathbf{C} .

There is an alternative for calculating the twin prime constant with accelerated convergence.

Since $[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2] = (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)$, Eq. (3) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P}) = (1-1/2^2)^{-1}(1-1/2^2)(1-1/3^2)(1-1/5^2) \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2) \times [(1-1/2^2)/(1-1/3^2)][(1-1/4^2)/(1-1/5^2)] \dots [1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)$$

$$\sim (4/3)(\pi^2/6)^{-1} \times \mathbf{R}_U(\mathbf{P}), \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_U(\mathbf{P}) = [(1-1/2^2)/(1-1/3^2)][(1-1/4^2)/(1-1/5^2)][(1-1/6^2)/(1-1/7^2)] \dots [1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2) \quad (6)$$

Since $[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2) < 1$ for $\mathbf{P} > 2$, $\mathbf{R}_U(\mathbf{P})$ decreases as \mathbf{P} increases. Thus, every value of $\mathbf{R}_U(\mathbf{P})$ with a finite \mathbf{P} represents an upper bound of \mathbf{C} . For example, $\mathbf{R}_U(59) = 0.814491$, $\mathbf{R}_U(101) = 0.8144571$, $\mathbf{R}_U(157) = 0.8144491 \Rightarrow \mathbf{C}(59) = 0.660202$, $\mathbf{C}(101) = 0.660174$, $\mathbf{C}(157) = 0.6601664$, while Eq. (4) results in $\mathbf{C}(59) = 0.662340$, $\mathbf{C}(101) = 0.661311$, $\mathbf{C}(157) = 0.660841$. It's obvious that use of $\mathbf{R}_U(\mathbf{P})$ in Eqs. (6) to calculate \mathbf{C} in Eq. (5) can converge faster, as shown in Fig. 1.

Combining Eqs. (4) & (5) results in

$$\mathbf{\Pi_{TP}(N)} \sim (16/\pi^2) \times \mathbf{R_U(P)} \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 \quad (7)$$

For = $\mathbf{P} = 59, 101 \text{ \& } 157$,

$$1.320403 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 > 1.320348 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 > 1.320333 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 > \mathbf{\Pi_{TP}(N)}. \quad (8)$$

To find the lower bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi_{TP}(N)}$, it's necessary to rewrite Eq. (3) as follows:

$$1-2/\mathbf{P} = (1-1/\mathbf{P})^2(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^2[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^2 \quad (9)$$

Let

$$\mathbf{R_L(P)} = [(1-1/4^2)/(1-1/5^2)^2][(1-1/6^2)/(1-1/7^2)^2]..... [1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^2 \quad (10)$$

Then, Eq. (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C(P)} &= (1-1/2^2)^2(1-1/2^2)^2(1-1/3^2)^2(1-1/5^2)^2.... (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^2 \times [(1-1/2^2)/(1-1/3^2)^2][(1-1/4^2)/(1-1/5^2)^2]....[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^2 \\ &\sim (27/16)(\pi^2/6)^{-2} \times \mathbf{R_L(P)} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Since $[1-1/(\mathbf{P}-1)^2]/(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^2 > 1$ for $\mathbf{P} > 3$, $\mathbf{R_L(P)}$ increases as \mathbf{P} or \mathbf{N} increases. For example,

$$\mathbf{R_L(59)} = 1.055176 < \mathbf{R_L(101)} = 1.056731 < \mathbf{R_L(157)} = 1.057457 < \mathbf{R_L(P)}, \text{ and}$$

$$1.316139 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 < 1.318078 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 < 1.318984 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 < \mathbf{\Pi_{TP}(N)} \quad (12)$$

Thus, Eqs. (8) & (12) =>

$$1.318984 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 < \mathbf{\Pi_{TP}(N)} < 1.320333 \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 \quad (13)$$

Fig. 1 shows calculated $2\mathbf{C(P)}$ values vs. prime numbers up to 293 with different methods. It's clear that both positive lower and upper bounds exist with a very small difference or converge to the same non-zero positive limit, implying the existence of infinite twin prim pairs.

Fig. 1. Calculated $2C(P)$ values vs. prime numbers

IV. Prime k-tuple Distribution

Similar sieve methods are applicable to prime k -tuples, including 1-tuple prime number, cousin prime, sexy prime, $(p, p+2, p+6)$, $(p, p+2, p+6, p+8)$, $(p, p+2, p+6, p+8, p+12)$, etc..

Let $m_0 < m_1 < m_2 < m_3 < \dots < m_{k-1}$ be even integers, $p_1 < p_2 < p_3 < \dots < P < \dots$ be all the prime numbers in order, i.e. $p_1=2, p_2=3, p_3=5, p_4=7 \dots$ etc., p_j be the greatest prime less than or equal to k for $k > 2$, and $h_k(p)$ be the number of the incongruent residues of $\{m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{k-1}\}$ with respect to modulo prime p . Apparently, $h_k(p) \leq k$. A k -tuple of the form $(2n+1+m_0, 2n+1+m_1, 2n+1+m_2, 2n+1+m_3, \dots, 2n+1+m_{k-1})$ can possibly be a prime k -tuple with the sieving procedure. After sieving out n numbers that belong to $h_k(p)$ residue classes modulo p for all prime numbers $3 \leq p \leq P$ such that $2n+1+m_i \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for all $0 \leq i \leq k-1$, the n value distribution function, $D_{kP}(P)$ for $P \geq k$, is

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{kP}(P) &= \left[\frac{(p_2 - h_k(p_2))}{p_2} \right] \left[\frac{(p_3 - h_k(p_3))}{p_3} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(P - h_k(P))}{P} \right] \\
 &= \left[\frac{g}{(p_2 p_3 \dots p_j)} \right] F_{cr}(P) (1 - k/p_{j+1}) (1 - k/p_{j+2}) (1 - k/p_{j+3}) \dots (1 - k/P)
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where $g = \left[\frac{(p_2 - h_k(p_2))}{p_2} \right] \left[\frac{(p_3 - h_k(p_3))}{p_3} \right] \dots \left[\frac{(p_j - h_k(p_j))}{p_j} \right]$, and

$$F_{cr}(P) = f_{cr}(p_{j+1}) f_{cr}(p_{j+2}) \dots f_{cr}(P) \text{ with } f_{cr}(p) = \frac{(p - h_k(p))}{(p - k)}.$$

It's obvious that $g \geq 0$ is an integer constant depending on the k -tuple, and $F_{cr}(P) \geq 1$ is a function with rational values. $h_k(p) = k$ & $f_{cr}(p) = \frac{(p - k)}{(p - k)} = 1$ for all prime numbers $p > d = m_{k-1} - m_0 > k$, and, thus, $F_{cr}(P)$ also becomes a constant when $P > d > k$.

To calculate upper and lower bounds, $1 - k/P$ is expressed in the following 3 different equations.

$$1 - k/P = \frac{(P - k)}{P} = \left[\frac{(P-1)}{P} \right]^k \left[\frac{P^{k-1}(P-k)}{(P-1)^k} \right] \tag{15}$$

$$= (1 - 1/P)^k (1 - 1/P^2)^y \left[\frac{P^{2y+k-1}(P-k)}{(P-1)^{y+k}(P+1)^y} \right] \tag{16}$$

$$= (1-1/\mathbf{P})^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}[\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+1}(\mathbf{P}-\mathbf{k})]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+1}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{\mathbf{y}+1}], \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{y} is a positive integer such that $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{P}-\mathbf{k})]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{\mathbf{y}}] < 1$ for \mathbf{P} greater than a certain number, and $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+1}(\mathbf{P}-\mathbf{k})]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+1}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{\mathbf{y}+1}] > 1$ for \mathbf{P} greater than another certain number.

To calculate \mathbf{y} value, it's necessary to expand the numerator and the denominator of $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P})$ into polynomials, as follows:

$$\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) = (\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}} - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-1})/[(\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}} - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-1}) + \mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-2}(\mathbf{k}^2-\mathbf{k}-2\mathbf{y})/2 + \mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-3}(6\mathbf{k}\mathbf{y}-\mathbf{k}^3+3\mathbf{k}^2-2\mathbf{k})/6 + \dots]$$

Let the coefficient of $\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-2}$ in the denominator equal to zero, i.e.

$$(\mathbf{k}^2-\mathbf{k}-2\mathbf{y})/2 = 0 \Rightarrow \mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{k}^2-\mathbf{k})/2. \text{ Thus, } \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) \text{ becomes}$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) = (\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}} - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-1})/[(\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}} - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-1}) + \mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-3}(\mathbf{k}^3-\mathbf{k})/3 + \dots]$$

Since $(\mathbf{k}^3-\mathbf{k})/3 > 0$ for $\mathbf{k} > 1$, the coefficient of $\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-3}$ is greater than zero, and $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) < 1$ is an increasing function for \mathbf{P} greater than a certain number.

With $\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{k}^2-\mathbf{k})/2$, $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{P})$ becomes

$$\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{P}) = (\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+2} - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+1})/[(\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+2} - \mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}+1}) - \mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}} + \mathbf{P}^{2\mathbf{y}+\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{k}^3+2\mathbf{k})/3 + \dots].$$

$\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{P}) > 1$ is a decreasing function for \mathbf{P} greater than another certain number.

Combining Eqs. (14) & (16) to find upper bounds of the distribution =>

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{P}) &= [\mathbf{g}/(\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_3\dots\mathbf{p}_j)]\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})[(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}}]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}}](1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+1})^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+2})^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+1}^2)^{\mathbf{y}}(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+2}^2)^{\mathbf{y}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{\mathbf{y}} \times \\ &\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+1})\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+2})\dots\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &\sim [\mathbf{g}/(\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_3\dots\mathbf{p}_j)]\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})[(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}}]^{-1} \times [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-\mathbf{k}}(\pi^2/6)^{-\mathbf{y}} \times \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+1})\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+2})\dots\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) > 0$ is a decreasing function for \mathbf{P} greater than a certain number.

The total number of the prime \mathbf{k} -tuples in which all the elements are less than a very large natural number, $\mathbf{N} \sim \mathbf{P}^2$, is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N}) &= (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{P}) \sim (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &\sim [\mathbf{g}\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{N}/(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)][(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+1}^2)^{\mathbf{y}}]^{-1}[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-\mathbf{k}}(\pi^2/6)^{-\mathbf{y}}\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{P}) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

With different large \mathbf{P} values, Eq. (19) is useful for calculating upper bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N})$.

For lower bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N})$, combining Eqs. (14) & (17) with $\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{k}^2-\mathbf{k})/2$ results in

$$\mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{g}/(\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_3\dots\mathbf{p}_j)]\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})[(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}] (1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+1})^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+2})^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+1}^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+2}^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1} \times \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+1})\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+2})\dots\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{P})$$

$$\sim [\mathbf{g}/(\mathbf{p}_2\mathbf{p}_3\dots\mathbf{p}_j)]\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})[(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}]^{-1} \times [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-\mathbf{k}} (\pi^2/6)^{-\mathbf{y}-1} \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{P}) \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+1})\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{p}_{j+2})\dots\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{P})$ is an increasing function for \mathbf{P} greater than another certain number. Thus,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{P})$$

$$\sim [\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{N}/(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)][(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}]^{-1}[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-\mathbf{k}} (\pi^2/6)^{-\mathbf{y}-1} \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{P}) \quad (21)$$

With different large \mathbf{P} values, Eq. (21) is useful for calculating lower bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N})$.

$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N})$ can also be directly calculated by combining Eqs. (14) & (15) so that

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim [\mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{N}/(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)][(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}]^{-1}[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-\mathbf{k}} [\mathbf{p}_{j+1}^{\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{p}_{j+1}-\mathbf{k})/(\mathbf{p}_{j+1}-1)^{\mathbf{k}}] [\mathbf{p}_{j+2}^{\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{p}_{j+2}-\mathbf{k})/(\mathbf{p}_{j+2}-1)^{\mathbf{k}}]\dots[\mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{P}-\mathbf{k})/(\mathbf{P}-1)^{\mathbf{k}}] \quad (22)$$

However, the convergence is slower.

Eqs. (19), (21) & (22) can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathbf{kP}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim \mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (23)$$

where

$$\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P}) = [(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}]^{-1}[\mathbf{p}_{j+1}^{\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{p}_{j+1}-\mathbf{k})/(\mathbf{p}_{j+1}-1)^{\mathbf{k}}] [\mathbf{p}_{j+2}^{\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{p}_{j+2}-\mathbf{k})/(\mathbf{p}_{j+2}-1)^{\mathbf{k}}]\dots[\mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{k}-1}(\mathbf{P}-\mathbf{k})/(\mathbf{P}-1)^{\mathbf{k}}]$$

$$\sim [(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_{j+1}^2)^{\mathbf{y}}]^{-1} (\pi^2/6)^{-\mathbf{y}} \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{kU}}(\mathbf{P})$$

$$\sim [(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)(1-1/2)^{\mathbf{k}}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j)^{\mathbf{k}}(1-1/2^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{p}_j^2)^{\mathbf{y}+1}]^{-1} (\pi^2/6)^{-\mathbf{y}-1} \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{kL}}(\mathbf{P})$$

$\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P})$, depending on \mathbf{k} , has positive upper & lower bounds that have very small differences and converge to the same limit, i.e. $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{k}}$ as \mathbf{P} goes infinity. Eq. (23) is the same as that of the prime \mathbf{k} -tuple conjecture.

The sieve methods have provided a mean to identify if there is none, single one or infinitely many a prime \mathbf{k} -tuple of the form $(\mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_0, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_1, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_2, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_3, \dots, \mathbf{t}+\mathbf{m}_{\mathbf{k}-1})$, where \mathbf{t} is an odd natural number. If all elements in the \mathbf{k} -tuple form a complete system of incongruent residues of at least one prime number \mathbf{p} , then $\mathbf{h}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{p})=\mathbf{p} \Rightarrow \mathbf{gF}_{\mathbf{cr}}(\mathbf{P})=0$, and, thus, the only possible lone prime \mathbf{k} -tuple of this particular form is the one that contains \mathbf{p} . In order for the lone prime \mathbf{k} -tuple to exist, all other elements must also be primes. For example, there is no prime 6-tuple of the form $(\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{t}+2, \mathbf{t}+4, \mathbf{t}+6, \mathbf{t}+12, \mathbf{t}+14)$ because

$h_6(3)=3$, and the 6-tuple containing 3, (3, 5, 7, 9, 15, 17) has non-prime elements 9 & 15; (5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19) is a lone prime 6-tuple because $h_6(5)=5$, and all its elements are primes.

If $\{m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{k-1}\}$ is admissible, i.e. it does not form any complete incongruent residue system of all primes, then both g & $F_{cr}(P)$ are greater or equal to 1. Since N is greater than $[\ln(N)]^k$ for a finite k value, there are infinitely many prime k -tuples of the admissible form $(t+m_0, t+m_1, t+m_2, t+m_3, \dots, t+m_{k-1})$, and it's impossible for a prime k -tuple of any form to have only finite counts greater than one. For example, there are infinitely many prime 6-tuples of the form $(t, t+2, t+6, t+8, t+18, t+20)$ because there is no prime p such that $h_k(p)=p$. For a 2-tuple $(2n+1, 2n+1+2m)$ where n & m are natural numbers, $g=1$ & $F_{cr}(P) \geq 1$. Therefore, Alphonse de Polignac's conjecture[5] that every even number is equal to the difference of two consecutive prime numbers in an infinite number of ways is confirmed.

Though the above mentioned $m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{k-1}$ are all even numbers, introduction of g & $F_{cr}(P)$ is also applicable when $\{m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{k-1}\}$ contains both even and odd numbers, and k -tuples can be of the form $(n+m_0, n+m_1, n+m_2, n+m_3, \dots, n+m_{k-1})$. Let $m_0=0$ without losing generality, then the sieving procedure starting from $p_1=2$ can remove the even n values for the infinite prime k -tuples. When $\{m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{k-1}\}$ contains both even and odd numbers, $h_k(2)=2 \Rightarrow g=0$. Thus, there is none or only a lone prime k -tuples that must contain prime number, 2, e.g. (2, 3), (2, 3, 5, ...), (2, 7), (2, 37), (2, 11, 29, ...) etc..

V. Conclusion and Discussion

Sieve methods for generating prime k -tuples, including twin primes, cousin primes, sexy primes, etc., have been disclosed. By direct counting based on indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the actual counts of different prime k -tuples are calculated after the sieve procedures. The results, with mathematical approximations for analytic expressions but no conjectures, seem to match well with those of the prior conjectures which were mostly based on probabilities and complex methods.

The results have shown that the total number, $\Pi_{kp}(N)$, of a prime k -tuple in natural numbers up to N is approximately proportional to $1/[\ln(N)]^k$. The main reason is because there is a $(1-1/P)^k$ factor in Eqs. (15), (16) & (17). Both Eqs. (15) & (16) result in positive upper bounds, and Eq. (17) results in positive lower bounds. These upper & lower bounds tend to converge to the same limit when N goes to infinity. Attempt to make $\Pi_{kp}(N)$ proportional to $1/[\ln(N)]^{k'}$, where k' differs from k , leads to a zero or infinite proportional constant.

Introduction of g & $F_{cr}(P)$ provides an effective method to determine if there exists none, single one or infinitely many a prime k -tuple of the form $(n+m_0, n+m_1, n+m_2, n+m_3, \dots, n+m_{k-1})$, where n and $m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots, m_{k-1}$ are natural numbers with no restriction to be even or odd. If $gF_{cr}(P)=0$, there is none or a single prime k -tuple. Otherwise, $gF_{cr}(P) \geq 1 \Rightarrow$ there is infinitely many a prime k -tuple. No other finite count for prime k -tuples of any particular form is possible. According to the present theory, $g=1$ & $F_{cr}(P) \geq 1$ for all 2-tuples of the form $(t, t+2m)$, where t & m are natural numbers. Therefore,

the prime 2-tuple counting functions which includes \mathbf{g} & $\mathbf{F}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})$ values, confirms Alphonse de Polignac's conjecture[5] that every even number is equal to the difference of two consecutive prime numbers in an infinite number of ways.

In general, $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})$ values represent the counts relative to that of a prime \mathbf{k} -tuple with $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})=1$. For example, $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})=1$ for twin primes and $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})$ values of 1 & 2 for cousin & sexy primes, respectively, are the relative counts. Several theoretical $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})$ values for different prime 2-tuples & 3-tuples have been verified by actual counts, as shown below:

prime 2-tuple	(p, p+2)	(p, p+4)	(p, p+6)	(p, p+8)	(p, p+10)	(p, p+12)	(p, p+14)	(p, p+30)
counts up to ~2900	79	83	163	82	110	155	100	208
relative counts	1.0000	1.0506	2.0633	1.0380	1.3924	1.9620	1.2658	2.6329
theoretical	1	1	2	1	4/3	2	6/5	8/3

prime 3-tuple	(p, p+2, p+6)	(p, p+2, p+8)	(p, p+4, p+10)	(p, p+6, p+10)	(p, p+10, p+30)
counts up to ~2900	27	29	45	39	55
relative counts	1.0000	1.0741	1.6667	1.4444	2.0370
theoretical	1	1	3/2	3/2	2

For $\mathbf{P}=53$, $\mathbf{N}=\mathbf{P}^2\sim 2900$ and $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})=1$, the calculated counts of $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2)$ and $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+6)$ based on the past conjecture or this theory with mathematical approximations are $\mathbf{\Pi}_{TP}(2900)\sim 66$ & $\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(2900)\sim 21$ which are less than the actual counts of 79 & 27, respectively. However, the calculated counts based on the most accurate expression without mathematical approximations are $\mathbf{\Pi}_{TP}(2900)\sim 76$ & $\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(2900)\sim 27$ which are much closer to the actual counts.

While the accuracy of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{N})$ in Eq. (23) can be further improved with more computer aided calculations, there are some intrinsic errors. When \mathbf{N} is not large, the most significant error is from the replacement of $[(1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5)(1-1/7)\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})]^{-1} \sim 1+1/2+1/3+1/4+1/5+\dots+1/\mathbf{N}$ to $\ln(\mathbf{N})\sim \ln(\mathbf{P}^2)$. For example when $\mathbf{P} = 17$, $[(1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5)(1-1/7)\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})]^{-1} \sim 10.26$ while $\ln(\mathbf{P}^2) \sim 11.36$, about 10% discrepancy. Thus, Eq. (23) results in more than 10% under estimation. For twin prime pairs, this error and neglecting $\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{P})$ together might result in >25% under estimation if \mathbf{P} is not large enough. The actual number of twin prime pairs might be about $1.7\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2$, instead of $1.32\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2$. For example, there are 16 twin prime pairs that are less than $289 = 17^2$, not including the 3 & 5 pair. While $1.3 \times 289/[\ln(289)]^2 = 11.9$, $1.7 \times 289/[\ln(289)]^2 = 15.3$ which is close to the actual 16 twin prime pairs.

Replacement of $1+1/2+1/3+1/4+1/5+\dots+1/\mathbf{N}$ by $\ln(\mathbf{N})$ also results in a small error since $\ln(\mathbf{N}) + 0.5-0.5/(\mathbf{N}+1) < 1+1/2+1/3+1/4+1/5+\dots+1/\mathbf{N} < \ln(\mathbf{N}) + \pi^2/12-0.5/(\mathbf{N}+1)$.

A more accurate equation is to employ Eq. (14) directly for $\mathbf{D}_{kP}(\mathbf{P})$ without neglecting $\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{P})$, i.e.

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{N}) \sim [\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{N}/(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)] \times (1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{j+1})(1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{j+2})(1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{j+3})\dots\dots(1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{P}), \text{ or} \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{N}) \sim \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^k + \mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{P}), \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{P}^2 \sim \mathbf{N}$.

For twin prime pairs, $\mathbf{g} = 1$, $\mathbf{F}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}) = 1$, and $\mathbf{p}_j = 2$. Thus,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{TP}(\mathbf{N}) \sim (\mathbf{N}/2) \times (1-2/3)(1-2/5)(1-2/7)(1-2/11)\dots\dots(1-2/\mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{\Pi}_{TP}(\mathbf{P}) \quad (26)$$

$$\sim \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^k + \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}^{1/2})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}^{1/2}) \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/[\ln(\mathbf{N}^{1/2})]^k + \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}^{1/4})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}^{1/4}) \times \mathbf{N}^{1/4}/[\ln(\mathbf{N}^{1/4})]^k + \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}^{1/8})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}^{1/8}) \times \mathbf{N}^{1/8}/[\ln(\mathbf{N}^{1/8})]^k + \dots\dots \quad (26.a)$$

$$\sim [\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{N} + 2^k\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}^{1/2})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}^{1/2})\mathbf{N}^{1/2} + 4^k\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}^{1/4})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}^{1/4})\mathbf{N}^{1/4} + 8^k\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P}^{1/8})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}^{1/8})\mathbf{N}^{1/8} + \dots\dots]/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^k \quad (26.b)$$

With $\mathbf{P} = 17$ and $\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{P}^2 = 289$, the actual $\mathbf{\Pi}_{TP}(\mathbf{P}) = 3$ and Eq. (26) results in $\mathbf{\Pi}_{TP}(289) = 12.6 + 3 = 15.6$ which is closer to the actual. The error is caused by the non-dividable integers. Therefore, Eq. (26) should be very accurate for larger \mathbf{N} & \mathbf{P} .

Eq. (26) can be implemented to prove there is at least a twin prime pair in between \mathbf{P} & $2\mathbf{P}$ for a large prime number \mathbf{P} , and, thus, at least a twin prime pair in between \mathbf{t} & $2\mathbf{t}$ where \mathbf{t} is a large natural number. There is also many a twin prime pair in between \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{P}^2 .

Eqs. (24) & (25) are valid for any \mathbf{N} value between \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{P}^2 as long as all the elements in the \mathbf{k} -tuples are less than \mathbf{P}^2 . If $\mathbf{P} < \mathbf{N} < \mathbf{N} + d\mathbf{N} < \mathbf{P}^2$ where $d\mathbf{N}$ is a positive number, then the number of prime \mathbf{k} -tuples in between \mathbf{N} & $\mathbf{N} + d\mathbf{N}$ is

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{N} + d\mathbf{N}) - \mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{N}) \sim [\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})(d\mathbf{N})/(\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{p}_j)] \times (1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{j+1})(1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{j+2})(1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{p}_{j+3})\dots\dots(1-\mathbf{k}/\mathbf{P})$$

$$\sim \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}) \times d\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^k, \text{ resulting in}$$

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{kP}(\mathbf{N}) \sim \mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})\mathbf{C}_k(\mathbf{P}) \times \int_2^{\mathbf{N}} 1/[\ln(\mathbf{s})]^k d\mathbf{s} \quad (27)$$

It's known that Eqs. (23) - (27) have intrinsic errors due to mathematical equation approximations if \mathbf{N} is not large enough. There is another error depending on $\mathbf{d}=\mathbf{m}_{k-1}-\mathbf{m}_0$ of the \mathbf{k} -tuple. If \mathbf{d} is huge, there is a large error even when \mathbf{N} is very large.

For example, let $\mathbf{d}=\mathbf{p}_1\mathbf{p}_2\dots\mathbf{P}_x$, where \mathbf{P}_x is a very large prime number. Then, the calculated $\mathbf{\Pi}_{2P}(\mathbf{N})$ with $\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{P}_x^2$ for 2-tuple $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+\mathbf{d})$ appears to be approximately proportional to $\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]$, which could be much larger than $\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2$ of the twin prime. However, there is actually zero prime 2-tuple of the form $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+\mathbf{d})$ within 1 to $\mathbf{N} = \mathbf{P}_x^2$ since $\mathbf{p}+\mathbf{d}$ does not meet the condition that $\mathbf{p}+\mathbf{d} < \mathbf{P}_x^2$. Therefore, \mathbf{N} needs to be much larger than \mathbf{d} in order for the above equations to be accurate. In fact, the counting function of this prime 2-tuple for a very large $\mathbf{N} \sim \mathbf{P}^2 \gg \mathbf{P}_x^2$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{2p}(N) &\sim (N/2) \times [(1-1/3)(1-1/5)\dots(1-1/P_x)(1-2/P_{x+1})][(1-2/P_{x+2})\dots(1-2/P)] + \Pi_{2p}(P) \\ &\sim (N/2) \times (1-1/2)^{-1}(1-1/2)(1-1/3)(1-1/5)\dots(1-1/P_x)[(1-2/3)(1-2/5)\dots(1-2/P_x)]^{-1}(1-2/3)(1-2/5)\dots(1-2/P_x)(1-2/P_{x+1})(1-2/P_{x+2})\dots(1-2/P) \\ &\sim N \times [1/\ln(P_x^2)] \times [4C(P_x)]^{-1}[\ln(P_x^2)]^2 \times 2C(P)/[\ln(N)]^2 \\ &\sim \ln(P_x^2)[4C(P_x)]^{-1} \times 2C(P) \times N/[\ln(N)]^2 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $g_{F_{cr}(P)C_k(P)} \sim \ln(P_x^2)/[4C(P_x)]$ in this case, and there are much more $(p, p+d)$ prime 2-tuples than twin prime pairs when N is much larger than d . It might appear that there are much more pairs of prime 2-tuples when the 2 elements are loosely entangled with a very large distance $d=p_1p_2\dots P_x$. This is also similar for prime k -tuples of the form $(p, p+d, p+2d, p+3d, \dots, p+(k-1)d)$. However, a k -tuple with a very large distance does not necessary have more pairs than others. For example, let $d=2^{33}\sim 10^{10}$, which is much larger than 10^7 in Zhang's paper. Then, the prime counting function of $(p, p+2^{33})$ is still about the same as that of the twin primes for $N \gg d$. Another example is for $d=2 \times 3^{21} > 10^{10}$, the prime counting function of $(p, p+2 \times 3^{21})$ is about the same as that of the sexy primes for $N \gg d$.

Though $D_{kp}(P)$ has been referred as a distribution function, it is not the probability of a random variable. It's true that the probability of the outcome without 2 undesired points is 4/6 when one tosses dice. There is no guaranty that the actual outcome ratio is 4/6 due to uncertainty. However, if there are 6 dice with the first one having one point facing up, the second one having 2 points facing up, etc., removing 2 undesired dice leaves 4 dice with exactly the desired 4 different points up. The sieve procedures remove undesired residue classes, resulting in a precise ratio of the remaining numbers to the original ones without random fluctuation according to the indication of the Chinese remainder theorem. If one has the patience or a powerful computer to carry out all the detailed calculation for prime k -tuple counts by sifting the n numbers up to $\sim N/2$ with the sieve methods described in this paper, there will be no random fluctuation errors except those caused by non-dividable numbers. Since N can be much larger than $[\ln(N)]^k$ for a finite k value if N is large enough, there are still infinite counts of prime k -tuples after excluding the errors caused by non-dividable numbers.

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VII. References

1. Zhang, Yitang (2014), "Bounded gaps between primes", *Annals of Mathematics*, 179 (3): 1121–1174.
2. Thomas, Kelly Devine (Summer 2014), "Yitang Zhang's spectacular mathematical journey", *The Institute Letter*, Princeton, NJ: Institute for Advanced Study

3. Tao, Terence (4 June 2013), "Polymath proposal: Bounded gaps between primes".
4. Tao, Terry, Ph.D. (presenter) (7 October 2014), Small and large gaps between the primes (video lecture), UCLA Department of Mathematics – via YouTube
5. Alphonse de Polignac, A. (1849), "Recherches nouvelles sur les nombres premiers" [New research on prime numbers], Comptes rendus (in French), 29: 397–401.

VIII. Appendices: Examples of prime k-tuples

Similar sieve methods are also applicable to other prime **k**-tuples, such as **(p, p+4)**, **(p, p+6)**, **(p, p+2, p+6)**, **(p, p+2, p+6, p+8)**, etc..

A. Prime 2-tuples:

While the distribution of **(p, p+4)** cousin primes is the same as that of twin primes, it's well known that the distribution of the 2-tuple **(p, p+6)** sexy primes is twice of that of the twin primes. This is because $h_2(3)=1 \Rightarrow F_{cr}(P)=f_{cr}(3)=2$ for sexy prime. It is also the same for **(p, p+12)**, **(p, p+18)**, etc..

Other examples that have distributions different from that of the twin primes are shown in the following:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{For } (p, p+10), g=1 \text{ and } h_2(5)=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{f_{cr}(5)}=4/3, \mathbf{f_{cr}(3)}=\mathbf{f_{cr}(7)}=\mathbf{f_{cr}(11)}= \dots \mathbf{f_{cr}(P)}=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{F_{cr}(P)}=(4/3) \Rightarrow \mathbf{\pi_{2p}(N)} \sim (4/3) \times 2\mathbf{C(P)} \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{For } (p, p+14), g=1 \text{ and } h_2(7)=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{f_{cr}(7)}=6/5, \mathbf{f_{cr}(3)}=\mathbf{f_{cr}(5)}=\mathbf{f_{cr}(11)}= \dots \mathbf{f_{cr}(P)}=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{F_{cr}(P)}=(6/5) \Rightarrow \mathbf{\pi_{2p}(N)} \sim (6/5) \times 2\mathbf{C(P)} \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{For } (p, p+30), g=1, h_2(3)=1 \text{ and } h_2(5)=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{f_{cr}(3)}=2, \mathbf{f_{cr}(5)}=4/3, \mathbf{f_{cr}(7)}=\mathbf{f_{cr}(11)}= \dots \mathbf{f_{cr}(P)}=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{F_{cr}(P)}=(8/3) \Rightarrow \mathbf{\pi_{2p}(N)} \sim (8/3) \times 2\mathbf{C(P)} \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{For } (p, p+70), g=1, h_2(5)=1 \text{ and } h_2(7)=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{f_{cr}(5)}=4/3, \mathbf{f_{cr}(7)}=6/5, \mathbf{f_{cr}(3)}=\mathbf{f_{cr}(11)}= \dots \mathbf{f_{cr}(P)}=1 \Rightarrow \\ &\mathbf{F_{cr}(P)}=(4/3)(6/5)=(8/5) \Rightarrow \mathbf{\pi_{2p}(N)} \sim (8/5) \times 2\mathbf{C(P)} \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 \end{aligned}$$

The $gF_{cr}(P)$ values for prime 2-tuples up to **(p, p+70)** are summarized below:

Let $\mathbf{A}_{3U}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^8(\mathbf{P}-3)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^6(\mathbf{P}+1)^3]$, and $\mathbf{A}_{3L}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{10}(\mathbf{P}-3)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^7(\mathbf{P}+1)^4]$. It can be shown that $\mathbf{A}_{3U}(\mathbf{P})$ is a decreasing function of \mathbf{P} , $\mathbf{A}_{3U}(\mathbf{P}) < 1$ for $\mathbf{P} \geq 5$, $\mathbf{A}_{3L}(\mathbf{P})$ is an increasing function of \mathbf{P} , and $\mathbf{A}_{3L}(\mathbf{P}) > 1$ for $\mathbf{P} \geq 11$.

Combining Eqs. (28) & (30) to find upper bounds of the distribution =>

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{3P}(\mathbf{P}) &= (1/3)[(1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3(1-1/2^2)^3(1-1/3^2)^3]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3(1-1/2^2)^3(1-1/3^2)^3](1-1/5)^3(1-1/7)^3 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^3 \\ &\quad (1-1/5^2)^3(1-1/7^2)^3 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^3 \times \mathbf{A}_{3U}(5)\mathbf{A}_{3U}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{3U}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &= (243/8) \times (1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3(1-1/5)^3(1-1/7)^3 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^3(1-1/2^2)^3(1-1/3^2)^3(1-1/5^2)^3(1-1/7^2)^3 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^3 \\ &\quad \times \mathbf{R}_{3U}(\mathbf{P}), \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{3U}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{3U}(5)\mathbf{A}_{3U}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{3U}(\mathbf{P})$ is a decreasing function of \mathbf{P} .

Thus, the total number of the 3-tuple primes less than a very large natural number, \mathbf{N} , is

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) = (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{3P}(\mathbf{P}) \sim (3280.5/\pi^6) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 \mathbf{R}_{3P}(\mathbf{P}) \quad (33)$$

For $\mathbf{P} = 59, 101, 157$, $\mathbf{R}_{3U}(59) = 0.837847$, $\mathbf{R}_{3U}(101) = 0.837706$, $\mathbf{R}_{3U}(157) = 0.837667$, respectively, and the corresponding $\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N})$ values are $2.858942\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$, $2.858462\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$, $2.858328\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$. Therefore,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) < 2.858328\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 < 2.858462\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 < 2.858942\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3. \quad (34)$$

These are the upper bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N})$.

For lower bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N})$, combining Eqs. (28) & (31) results in

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{3P}(\mathbf{P}) &= (1/3)[(1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3(1-1/2^2)^4(1-1/3^2)^4]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3(1-1/2^2)^4(1-1/3^2)^4](1-1/5)^3(1-1/7)^3 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^3 \\ &\quad (1-1/5^2)^4(1-1/7^2)^4 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^4 \times \mathbf{A}_{3L}(5)\mathbf{A}_{3L}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{3L}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &= (729/16) \times (1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3(1-1/5)^3(1-1/7)^3 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^3(1-1/2^2)^4(1-1/3^2)^4(1-1/5^2)^4(1-1/7^2)^4 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^4 \\ &\quad \times \mathbf{R}_{3L}(\mathbf{P}), \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{3L}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{3L}(5)\mathbf{A}_{3L}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{3L}(\mathbf{P})$ is an increasing function of \mathbf{P} . Thus,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) = (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{3P}(\mathbf{P}) \sim (29524.5/\pi^8) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 \mathbf{R}_{3L}(\mathbf{P}) \quad (36)$$

For $\mathbf{P} = 59, 101, 157$, $\mathbf{R}_{3L}(59) = 0.915835$, $\mathbf{R}_{3L}(101) = 0.917068$, $\mathbf{R}_{3L}(157) = 0.917666$, respectively, and the corresponding $\mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N})$ values are $2.849711\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$, $2.853547\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$, $2.855409\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$. Thus,

$$2.849711\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 < 2.853547\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 < 2.855409\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 < \mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) \quad (37)$$

$$\text{Eqs. (34) \& (37) } \Rightarrow 2.855409\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 < \mathbf{\Pi}_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) < 2.858328\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3 \quad (38)$$

$\Pi_{3P}(\mathbf{N})$ can also be directly calculated by combining Eqs. (28) & (29) so that

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) &\sim (\mathbf{N}/6) \times [(1-1/2)^3(1-1/3)^3]^{-1} [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-3} [5^2(5-3)/(5-1)^3] [7^2(7-3)/(7-1)^3] \dots [\mathbf{P}^2(\mathbf{P}-3)/(\mathbf{P}-1)^3] \\ &= 4.5\mathbf{N}[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-3} [5^2(5-3)/(5-1)^3] [7^2(7-3)/(7-1)^3] \dots [\mathbf{P}^2(\mathbf{P}-3)/(\mathbf{P}-1)^3] \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

However, the convergence is slower. Even with $\mathbf{P} = 293$, Eq. (39) results in $\Pi_{3P}(\mathbf{N}) \sim 2.862481\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^3$, which is still outside the upper and lower bounds in Eqs. (34) & (37) with $\mathbf{P} = 59$. To match Eq. (34), Eq. (39) needs to be calculated up to a larger \mathbf{P} value, as shown in Fig. 2.

For other prime 3-tuples, $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+8)$, $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+4, \mathbf{p}+10)$, $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+6, \mathbf{p}+10)$ & $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+10, \mathbf{p}+30)$, the $\mathbf{gF}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})$ values are 1, 1.5, 1.5 & 2, respectively.

Fig. 2. Calculated $\mathbf{C}_3(\mathbf{P})$ values vs. prime numbers

C. Prime 4-tuple $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+6, \mathbf{p}+8)$:

For the prime 4-tuple, $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+6, \mathbf{p}+8)$, e.g. (5, 7, 11, 13), (11, 13, 17, 19), etc., the possible ones must be of the form $(2\mathbf{n}+1, 2\mathbf{n}+3, 2\mathbf{n}+7, 2\mathbf{n}+9)$, where \mathbf{n} is a natural number.

A similar sieve method can be applied to sieve out \mathbf{n} numbers that belong to 4 of the residue classes modulo \mathbf{p} for all $\mathbf{p} \geq 5$ that satisfy the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} 2\mathbf{n}+1 &\equiv 0 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 2 \pmod{5} & 2\mathbf{n}+3 &\equiv 0 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \\ 2\mathbf{n}+7 &\equiv 0 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 4 \pmod{5} & 2\mathbf{n}+9 &\equiv 0 \pmod{5} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 3 \pmod{5} \\ 2\mathbf{n}+1 &\equiv 0 \pmod{7} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 3 \pmod{7} & 2\mathbf{n}+3 &\equiv 0 \pmod{7} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 2 \pmod{7} \\ 2\mathbf{n}+7 &\equiv 0 \pmod{7} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{7} & 2\mathbf{n}+9 &\equiv 0 \pmod{7} \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 6 \pmod{7} \\ & \text{etc..} & & \end{aligned}$$

In this case, $\mathbf{p}_j=3$, $\mathbf{g}=1$ and $\mathbf{F}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})=1$ for $\mathbf{P}>3$. After precluding with the sieve method up to a large prime number, \mathbf{P} , the distribution function, $\mathbf{D}_{4P}(\mathbf{P})$, of the numbers left is

$$\mathbf{D}_{4P}(\mathbf{P}) = (1/3)(1-4/5)(1-4/7)(1-4/11)(1-4/13)(1-4/17)\dots(1-4/\mathbf{P}) \quad (40)$$

$$1-4/\mathbf{P} = (\mathbf{P}-4)/\mathbf{P} = [(\mathbf{P}-1)/\mathbf{P}]^4[\mathbf{P}^3(\mathbf{P}-4)/(\mathbf{P}-1)^4] \quad (41)$$

$$= (1-1/\mathbf{P})^4(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^6[\mathbf{P}^{15}(\mathbf{P}-4)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{10}(\mathbf{P}+1)^6] \quad (42)$$

$$= (1-1/\mathbf{P})^4(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^7[\mathbf{P}^{17}(\mathbf{P}-4)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{11}(\mathbf{P}+1)^7] \quad (43)$$

Let $\mathbf{A}_{4U}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{15}(\mathbf{P}-4)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{10}(\mathbf{P}+1)^6]$, and $\mathbf{A}_{4L}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{17}(\mathbf{P}-3)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{11}(\mathbf{P}+1)^7]$. It can be shown that $\mathbf{A}_{4U}(\mathbf{P})$ is a decreasing function of \mathbf{P} , $\mathbf{A}_{4U}(\mathbf{P}) < 1$ for $\mathbf{P} \geq 5$, $\mathbf{A}_{4L}(\mathbf{P})$ is an increasing function of \mathbf{P} , and $\mathbf{A}_{4L}(\mathbf{P}) > 1$ for $\mathbf{P} > 23$.

Combining Eqs. (40) & (42) to find upper bounds of the distribution =>

$$\mathbf{D}_{4P}(\mathbf{P}) = (1/3)[(1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4(1-1/2^2)^6(1-1/3^2)^6]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4(1-1/2^2)^6(1-1/3^2)^6](1-1/5)^4(1-1/7)^4 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^4 (1-1/5^2)^6(1-1/7^2)^6 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^6 \times \mathbf{A}_{QU}(5)\mathbf{A}_{QU}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{QU}(\mathbf{P})$$

$$= (3^9/2^6) \times (1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4(1-1/5)^4(1-1/7)^4 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^4(1-1/2^2)^6(1-1/3^2)^6(1-1/5^2)^6(1-1/7^2)^6 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^6 \times \mathbf{R}_{4U}(\mathbf{P}), \quad (44)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{4U}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{4U}(5)\mathbf{A}_{4U}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{4U}(\mathbf{P})$ is a decreasing function of \mathbf{P} .

Thus, the total number of the 4-tuple primes less than a very large natural number, \mathbf{N} , is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi}_{4P}(\mathbf{N}) &= (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{4P}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &\sim (3^{15}/2 \pi^{12}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 \mathbf{R}_{4U}(\mathbf{P}) \sim 7.762299 \mathbf{R}_{4U}(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

For $\mathbf{P} = 59, 101, 157$, $\mathbf{R}_{4U}(59) = 0.535115$, $\mathbf{R}_{4U}(101) = 0.534888$, $\mathbf{R}_{4U}(157) = 0.534825$, respectively, and the corresponding $\mathbf{\Pi}_{4P}(\mathbf{N})$ values are $4.153722\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$, $4.151958\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$, $4.151469\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$. Thus,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{4P}(\mathbf{N}) < 4.151469\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 < 4.151958\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 < 4.153722\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4. \quad (46)$$

For lower bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{4P}(\mathbf{N})$, combining Eqs. (40) & (43) results in

$$\mathbf{D}_{4P}(\mathbf{P}) = (1/3)[(1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4(1-1/2^2)^7(1-1/3^2)^7]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4(1-1/2^2)^7(1-1/3^2)^7](1-1/5)^4(1-1/7)^4 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^4 (1-1/5^2)^7(1-1/7^2)^7 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^7 \times \mathbf{A}_{QL}(5)\mathbf{A}_{QL}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{QL}(\mathbf{P})$$

$$= (3^{10}/2^7) \times (1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4(1-1/5)^4(1-1/7)^4 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P})^4(1-1/2^2)^7(1-1/3^2)^7(1-1/5^2)^7(1-1/7^2)^7 \dots (1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^7 \times \mathbf{R}_{4L}(\mathbf{P}), \quad (47)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{4L}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{4L}(5)\mathbf{A}_{4L}(7) \dots \mathbf{A}_{4L}(\mathbf{P})$ is an increasing function of \mathbf{P} .

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\Pi}_{4P}(\mathbf{N}) &= (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{4P}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &\sim (3^{17}/2 \pi^{14}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 \mathbf{R}_{4L}(\mathbf{P}) \sim 7.078368 \mathbf{R}_{4L}(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

For $\mathbf{P} = 59, 101, 157$, $\mathbf{R}_{4\mathbf{L}}(59) = 0.584924$, $\mathbf{R}_{4\mathbf{L}}(101) = 0.585562$, $\mathbf{R}_{4\mathbf{L}}(157) = 0.585902$, respectively, and the corresponding $\mathbf{\pi}_{4\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N})$ values are $4.140310\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$, $4.144821\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$, $4.147230\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$. Thus,

$$4.140310\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 < 4.144821\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 < 4.147230\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 < \mathbf{\pi}_{4\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N}) \quad (49)$$

$$\text{Eqs. (46) \& (49) } \Rightarrow 4.147230\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 < \mathbf{\pi}_{4\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N}) < 4.151469\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4 \quad (50)$$

$\mathbf{\pi}_{4\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N})$ can be directly calculated by combining Eqs. (40) & (41) so that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{\pi}_{4\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N}) &\sim (\mathbf{N}/6) \times [(1-1/2)^4(1-1/3)^4]^{-1} [\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-4} [5^3(5-4)/(5-1)^4] [7^3(7-4)/(7-1)^4] \dots [\mathbf{P}^3(\mathbf{P}-4)/(\mathbf{P}-1)^4] \\ &= 13.5\mathbf{N}[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^{-4} [5^3(5-4)/(5-1)^4] [7^3(7-4)/(7-1)^4] \dots [\mathbf{P}^3(\mathbf{P}-4)/(\mathbf{P}-1)^4] \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

However, the convergence is slower. Even with $\mathbf{P} = 293$, Eq. (51) results in $\mathbf{\pi}_{4\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{N}) \sim 4.163498\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^4$, which is still outside the upper and lower bounds in Eqs. (46) & (49) with $\mathbf{P} = 59$. To match Eq. (46), Eq. (51) needs to be calculated up to a larger \mathbf{P} value, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Calculated $\mathbf{C}_4(\mathbf{P})$ values vs. prime numbers

D. Prime 5-tuples $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+6, \mathbf{p}+8, \mathbf{p}+12)$ & $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+10, \mathbf{p}+30, \mathbf{p}+40, \mathbf{p}+60)$:

Another example is the prime 5-tuple $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+6, \mathbf{p}+8, \mathbf{p}+12)$, e.g. (5, 7, 11, 13, 17), (11, 13, 17, 19, 23), etc.. The possible prime 5-tuple $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}+2, \mathbf{p}+6, \mathbf{p}+8, \mathbf{p}+12)$ must be of the form $(2\mathbf{n}+1, 2\mathbf{n}+3, 2\mathbf{n}+7, 2\mathbf{n}+9, 2\mathbf{n}+13)$.

A similar sieve method can be applied to sieve out \mathbf{n} numbers that belong to 5 of the residue classes modulo \mathbf{p} for all $\mathbf{p} \geq 7$ that satisfy the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} 2\mathbf{n}+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} &\Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 3 \pmod{7} & 2\mathbf{n}+3 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} &\Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 2 \pmod{7} \\ 2\mathbf{n}+7 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} &\Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 0 \pmod{7} & 2\mathbf{n}+9 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} &\Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 6 \pmod{7} \\ 2\mathbf{n}+13 \equiv 0 \pmod{7} &\Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \equiv 4 \pmod{7} & &\text{etc..} \end{aligned}$$

In this case, $\mathbf{p}_j=5$, $\mathbf{g}=1$, and $\mathbf{F}_{cr}(\mathbf{P})=1$ for $\mathbf{P}>5$. After precluding with the sieve method up to a large prime number, \mathbf{P} , the distribution function, $\mathbf{D}_{5P}(\mathbf{P})$, of the numbers left is

$$\mathbf{D}_{5P}(\mathbf{P}) = [1/(3 \times 5)](1-5/7)(1-5/11)(1-5/13)(1-5/17)\dots(1-5/\mathbf{P}) \quad (52)$$

$$1-5/\mathbf{P} = (\mathbf{P}-5)/\mathbf{P} = [(\mathbf{P}-1)/\mathbf{P}]^5[\mathbf{P}^4(\mathbf{P}-5)/(\mathbf{P}-1)^5] \quad (53)$$

$$= (1-1/\mathbf{P})^5(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{10}[\mathbf{P}^{24}(\mathbf{P}-5)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{15}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{10}] \quad (54)$$

$$= (1-1/\mathbf{P})^5(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{11}[\mathbf{P}^{26}(\mathbf{P}-5)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{16}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{11}] \quad (55)$$

Let $\mathbf{A}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{24}(\mathbf{P}-5)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{15}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{10}]$, and $\mathbf{A}_{5L}(\mathbf{P}) = [\mathbf{P}^{26}(\mathbf{P}-5)]/[(\mathbf{P}-1)^{16}(\mathbf{P}+1)^{11}]$. It can be shown that $\mathbf{A}_{5U}(\mathbf{P})$ is a decreasing function of \mathbf{P} , $\mathbf{A}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) < 1$ for $\mathbf{P} \geq 5$, $\mathbf{A}_{5L}(\mathbf{P})$ is an increasing function of \mathbf{P} , and $\mathbf{A}_{5L}(\mathbf{P}) > 1$ for $\mathbf{P} > 23$.

Combining Eqs. (52) & (54) to find upper bounds of the distribution =>

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{5P}(\mathbf{P}) &= (1/15)[(1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1-1/2^2)^{10}(1-1/3^2)^{10}(1-1/5^2)^{10}]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1- \\ &1/2^2)^{10}(1-1/3^2)^{10}(1-1/5^2)^{10}](1-1/7)^5\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^5(1-1/7^2)^{10}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{10} \times \mathbf{A}_{5U}(7)\mathbf{A}_{5U}(11)\dots \mathbf{A}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &= 120.739112 \times (1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1-1/7)^5\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^5(1-1/2^2)^{10}(1-1/3^2)^{10}(1-1/5^2)^{10}(1- \\ &1/7^2)^{10}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{10} \times \mathbf{R}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &\sim 64321.56 (6/\pi^2)^{10} \times (1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1-1/7)^5\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^5 \times \mathbf{R}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{A}_{5U}(7)\mathbf{A}_{5U}(11)\dots \mathbf{A}_{5U}(\mathbf{P})$ is a decreasing function of \mathbf{P} .

Thus, the total number of the 5-tuple primes less than a very large natural number, \mathbf{N} , is

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{5P}(\mathbf{N}) = (\mathbf{N}/2) \times \mathbf{D}_{5P}(\mathbf{P}) \sim 14.782585\mathbf{R}_{5U}(\mathbf{P}) \times \mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5 \quad (57)$$

For $\mathbf{P} = 59, 101, 157$, $\mathbf{R}_{5U}(59) = 0.686235$, $\mathbf{R}_{5U}(101) = 0.685645$, $\mathbf{R}_{5U}(157) = 0.685483$, respectively, and the corresponding $\mathbf{\Pi}_{5P}(\mathbf{N})$ values are $10.144320\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5$, $10.135611\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5$, $10.133208\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5$. Thus,

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{5P}(\mathbf{N}) < 10.133208\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5 < 10.135611\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5 < 10.144320\mathbf{N}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^5. \quad (58)$$

For lower bounds of $\mathbf{\Pi}_{5P}(\mathbf{N})$, combining Eqs. (52) & (55) results in

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{5P}(\mathbf{P}) &= (1/15)[(1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1-1/2^2)^{11}(1-1/3^2)^{11}(1-1/5^2)^{11}]^{-1}[(1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1- \\ &1/2^2)^{11}(1-1/3^2)^{11}(1-1/5^2)^{11}](1-1/7)^5\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^5(1-1/7^2)^{11}\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{11} \times \mathbf{A}_{5L}(7)\mathbf{A}_{5L}(11)\dots \mathbf{A}_{5L}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &= 100502.44 \times (1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1-1/7)^5\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^5(1-1/2^2)^{11}(1-1/3^2)^{11}(1-1/5^2)^{11}(1-1/7^2)^{11}\dots(1- \\ &1/\mathbf{P}^2)^{11} \times \mathbf{R}_{5L}(\mathbf{P}) \\ &\sim 100502.44 (6/\pi^2)^{11} \times (1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5(1-1/7)^5\dots(1-1/\mathbf{P})^5 \times \mathbf{R}_{5L}(\mathbf{P}), \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

where $R_{5L}(P) = A_{5L}(7)A_{5L}(11)\dots A_{5L}(P)$ is an increasing function of P .

Thus,

$$\pi_{5P}(N) = (N/2) \times D_{5P}(P) \sim 14.041771 R_{5L}(P) \times N / [\ln(N)]^5 \quad (60)$$

For $P = 59, 101, 157$, $R_{5L}(59) = 0.720106$, $R_{5L}(101) = 0.7205776$, $R_{5L}(157) = 0.720910$, respectively, and the corresponding $\pi_{5P}(N)$ values are $10.111563N / [\ln(N)]^5$, $10.118186N / [\ln(N)]^5$, $10.122859N / [\ln(N)]^5$. Thus,

$$10.111563N / [\ln(N)]^5 < 10.118186N / [\ln(N)]^5 < 10.122859N / [\ln(N)]^5 < \pi_{4P}(N) \quad (61)$$

$$\text{Eqs. (58) \& (61)} \Rightarrow 10.122859N / [\ln(N)]^5 < \pi_{5P}(N) < 10.133208N / [\ln(N)]^5 \quad (62)$$

$\pi_{5P}(N)$ can be directly calculated by combining Eqs. (52) & (53) so that

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{5P}(N) &\sim (N/30) \times [(1-1/2)^5(1-1/3)^5(1-1/5)^5]^{-1} [\ln(N)]^{-5} [7^4(7-5)/(7-1)^5] \dots [P^4(P-5)/(P-1)^5] \\ &\sim 24.719238N [\ln(N)]^{-5} [7^4(7-5)/(7-1)^5] \dots [P^4(P-5)/(P-1)^5] \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

However, the convergence is slower. Even with $P = 293$, Eq. (63) results in

$\pi_{5P}(N) \sim 10.182008N / [\ln(N)]^5$, which is still outside the upper and lower bounds in Eqs. (58) & (61) with $P = 59$. To match Eq. (58), Eq. (63) needs to be calculated up to a larger P value, as shown in Fig. 4.

For $(p, p+10, p+30, p+40, p+60)$, $p_j=5$, $h_5(5)=1 \Rightarrow g=4$, and $F_{cr}(P)=1$ for $P>5$. Therefore,

$$10.122859gN / [\ln(N)]^5 < \pi_{5P}(N) < 10.133208gN / [\ln(N)]^5 \Rightarrow$$

$$40.491436N / [\ln(N)]^5 < \pi_{5P}(N) < 40.532832N / [\ln(N)]^5$$

Fig. 4. Calculated $C_5(P)$ values vs. prime numbers